

THE RELATION BETWEEN SOCIODEMOGRAPHIC INFORMATION WITH RISK FACTORS AND COMPLICATIONS OF DIABETES MELLITUS AMONG TYPE 2 DIABETES PATIENTS

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Abstract

Background: Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus is a growing public health problem; world-wide prevalence is 11.11%. And it is associated with serious complications. Sociodemographic factors and lifestyle behaviors influence disease progression and complications.

Objective: To assess the association between sociodemographic factors, risk factors, and complications of Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus.

Material methods: A descriptive cross-sectional study was conducted among 207 Type 2 diabetic patients at Peoples Medical Civil Hospital Nawabshah. Patients aged above 30 years of both gender who consented to participate were included and patients with type 1 diabetes and other chronic illnesses unrelated to diabetes were excluded. Data were collected using a structured questionnaire and analyzed using SPSS version 25. Frequencies, percentages, and Chi-square tests were applied to determine the associations.

Results: The mean age of participants was 51.18 ± 10.73 years. Male participants were included 56.52% of sample, while females involved 43.48%. Age, gender, education, socioeconomic status, and residence were significantly associated with diabetes risk factors and complications (hypertension, kidney problems, vision impairment, delayed wound healing and weight changes). Male participants showed higher association in smoking, tobacco, and alcohol use. Rural and low-income participants experienced poorer self-care practices and higher complication rates. Education level demonstrated a strong association with risk factors and complications, Mean fasting blood glucose was 207.39 mg/dl, indicating poor glycemic control.

Conclusion: Findings of this study concluded that Sociodemographic characteristics, life style behaviors and environmental factors were significantly associated with the risk factors and complications of Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus. Poor glycemic control unhealthy lifestyle were common among patients especially

among rural, low education and income participants. Health education and improved access to healthcare are essential to reduce the burden of diabetes.

INTRODUCTION

Diabetes Mellitus (DM) is one of the most global public health problem, affecting millions of people worldwide. Diabetes mellitus is chronic and complex defect of metabolism that impair the insulin secretion and resistance characterized by hyperglycemia. Type 2 Diabetes known as non-insulin dependent-diabetes mellitus (NIDDM), type II, or adult related diabetes. In influencing of Type 2 DM interaction between genetic, environmental risk factors that influence DM are air pollution, water pollution (contaminate water) chemical exposure such as pesticides herbicides increased risk of DM and behavioral risk factors, Smoking and Engaging in little physical activity and diet play the crucial role in developing type 2 DM.

Diet in addition with a sedentary lifestyle are the primary cause of type 2 diabetes mellitus. Age and obesity are the main risk factors responsible for increasing in frequency of Diabetes. Particularly middle age individuals between 40 and 59 affected by diabetes at global scale. Ethnicity, family history, and genetic predisposition also play crucial role in developing DM. Economic instability and low education level affecting the development of diabetes because having no knowledge about disease are at higher risk of disease.

Patients with type 2 DM often experience Polydipsia (Excessive thirst) due to hyperglycemia, Polyuria (frequent urination), Polyphagia (increase in hunger), tiredness, slow healing, Poor eyesight, weight gain and weight loss are the significant symptoms of Type 2 DM, It also increases the risk of serious complications like heart attacks and strokes, Nephropathy (renal failure) and Retinopathy (blindness).

The prevalence in of DM Western countries which is estimated to affect 642 million people worldwide by 2040, its increasing prevalence is due to non-modifiable factors, such as the ageing, and modifiable factors like obesity and unhealthy lifestyle habits. Diabetes is one of rapidly expanding public health problem of 21st century,

537 million people are living with diabetes. It is projected by 2045, 783 million people will have DM worldwide.

This global public health problem affected 529 people affected in 2021 and predicted to reach 1.31 billion people by 2050 worldwide. Prevalence of diabetes at global level of age is 5% for 35-39 years, 10% for 45-49 years, and 15% for 55-59 year and doubled by 20% in 60-70 above years. The national age-standardized point prevalence of type 2 diabetes ranged from 2174.5 to 19876.8 cases per 100,000 population, American Samoa (19876.8), the Marshall Islands (19523.9) and Niue (16454.2) had the three highest ages standardized point prevalence of type 2 diabetes per 100,000 population in 2019.

Pakistan currently ranks fourth in diabetes prevalence and is expected to move to third place in the next 25 years, Pakistan among the top 10 countries for absolute increase in diabetes prevalence. Approximately 19 million adults are suffering from diabetes in Pakistan, 3 out of which 8.5 million are undiagnosed, Prevalence was 28.3% and 25.3% in urban and rural areas respectively, highest prevalence 32.3% was observed in Sindh

Type 2 diabetes mellitus is rapidly increasing global health problem involves morbidity, mortality ratio. Its prevalence continuously rising due to non-modifiable risk factors such as Aging and modifiable risk factors like sedentary life style, physical inactivity, diet, obesity and smoking. Type 2 DM causes serious complication including neuropathy, retinopathy, nephropathy and stroke also more than these. Therefore, this study is to investigating the major risk factors influencing the development of type 2 diabetes myelitis, and Prevention to reduce frequency of diabetes risk factor involves a combination of lifestyle changes, regular physical activity, balanced diet and management environmental risk factors.

MATERIAL & METHODS

This study is Descriptive Cross-sectional used to identify risk factors and complications of type 2

diabetes among diabetic patients. the study was conducted at the diabetes OPD, at Peoples Medical Civil Hospital Nawabshah. Data collection was over two months period of time from 17 November to 17 January 2026 after approval of Institutional Review Board (IRB). Sample size was 207 calculated by using open epi info software, the calculation was based on 95% confidence level, an estimated population

proportion of 50% and margin of error 5%. A non-probability sampling technique was used to select participants. The inclusion criteria included both male and female, patients diagnosed with T2DM, aged more than 30 and those who agreed, and the exclusion criteria included those who diagnosed as type 1 DM, Gestational diabetes, Chronic illness unrelated to DM and unwilling to participate.

RESULTS

Figure 1: Age of Respondents

Figure 2: Gender of respondents

Table 1: Association of Age with Diabetes Mellitus Complications

QUESTIONS	AGE		X ²	df	p. Value
	Yes	No			
Do you suffer from hypertension (High Blood Pressure)?	140	67	77.359	40	0.0001
Have you experienced kidney-related problems since diagnosis of diabetes?	62	145	65.389	40	0.007
Do you have vision problems attributed to diabetes?	130	77	58.836	40	0.028
Do you have issues with wound healing?	80	127	57.269	40	0.038
Have you feel weight loss?	114	93	55.073	40	0.057
Have you feel weight gain?	80	127	59.307	40	0.025

Table 2: Association of Gender with Diabetes Mellitus Risk Factors

Questions	Gender		X ²	df	P. Value
	Male	Female			
Do you smoke?	85	20	51.754	1	0.0001
Do you consume alcohol?	13	1	8.067	1	0.005
Do you use tobacco?	35	3	23.982	1	0.0001
Do you consume processed meat products (sausages, nuggets, deli meat etc)?	97	62	5.611	1	0.018

Figure 3: Occupation of Respondents

Figure 4: Fasting Blood Sugar Level

Table 3: Association of Residence with Risk factors and Complications

QUESTIONS	Residence		X ²	df	P. Value
	Rural	Urban			
Is Diabetes 2 in your family history?	77	68	6.808	1	0.009
Do you perform regular exercise?	26	29	5.870	2	0.053
If yes, type of exercise performed most frequently? Walking/Jogging/Running	28	28	5.779	2	0.056
Do you own a blood sugar testing meter at home?	39	42	6.886	2	0.032
Do you regularly monitor and record your blood sugar levels?	15	20	4.500	1	0.034
Any other type of medicine consumption?	70	36	4.526	1	0.033
Type of drinking water? (Filter Water/Tap Water)	14F 108T	66F 19T	92.512	1	0.0001
Have you experienced kidney-related problems since diagnosis of diabetes?	43	19	3.969	1	0.046
Do you have vision problems attributed to diabetes?	86	44	7.521	1	0.006
Do you have issues with wound healing?	57	23	8.168	1	0.004
Having a dental issue?	80	44	3.977	1	0.046

Table 4: Association of Socioeconomic Status with Risk Factors and Complications

Questions	Socioeconomic status		X ²	df	P. Value
	Poor	Middle			
Is Diabetes 2 in your family history?					
Having diabetes affects daily routines?	40	105	12.506	1	0.0001
Do you smoke?	59	84	7.77	1	0.007
Type of drinking water? (Filter Water/Tap Water)	44	61	7.14	1	0.043
Do you suffer from hypertension (High Blood Pressure)?	58	69	15.180	1	.001
Have you experienced kidney related problems	50	84	4.247	1	0.039

Table 5: Education Association with Risk Factors and Complication

QUESTIONS	Education				X ²	df	P. Value
	Illiterate	Primary	Middle	Inter			
Is Diabetes 2 in your family history?	55	25	32	30	14.869	3	.002
Do you smoke?	30	15	26	34	7.546	3	0.056
Do you consume alcohol?	2	0	4	8	9.100	3	0.028
Do you do use tobacco?	6	10	9	13	9.225	3	0.026
Do you consume food items with additives/preservatives?	64	31	29	40	13.561	3	0.004
Do you take prescribed diabetes medications regularly?	42	20	28	24	9.605	3	0.022
Satisfactory sanitary system?	20	14	14	32	10.095	3	0.018
Type of drinking water? (Filter Water/Tap Water)	18F 56T	23F 20T	16F 24T	33F 27T	13.208	3	0.004
Do you suffer from hypertension (High Blood Pressure)?	58	29	25	28	17.380	3	0.001
Do you have vision problems attributed to diabetes?	55	20	30	25	18.294	3	0.0001
Have you experienced foot numbness, tingling, or loss of feeling?	61	26	34	37	10.440	3	0.015
Having a dental issue?	55	19	23	27	12.126	3	0.007

DISCUSSION

Regarding the demographical variables findings of this study, the mean age of the study participants was 51.18 years \pm 10.73, strong statistical associations between sociodemographic variables and both risk factors and complications of diabetes mellitus, Specifically, age was highly significantly linked to multiple complications, including hypertension, kidney-related problems vision problems, wound healing issues, weight loss, and weight gain. Significant gender differences were observed in behavioral risk factors, with males showing significantly higher rates of smoking, alcohol consumption, tobacco use and processed meat intake, despite males comprising 56.52% of the sample and female were 43.48%. Results of occupation of respondents showed that majority were housewives 138(38.65%), employed respondents were 56(27.05%), respondents who were unemployed 40(21.26%) and labor respondents were 27(13.04%). And the fasting blood sugar range was with the mean of 207.39 SD \pm 49.45.

Educational level was associated with family history of DM type 2, alcohol, tobacco, food additives, The consumption of processed meats has been consistently linked to an increased risk of T2DM due to their high content of saturated fats, sodium, and preservatives, medication adherence, sanitary conditions, and drinking water type, as well as complications like hypertension, vision problems, foot neuropathy, and dental issues. Residence correlated with risk factors such as family history, exercise habits (most were performing walking type of exercise), blood sugar monitoring, other medications, and notably drinking water type most of tap drinking water patterns shown in recent research that place of residence influence both access to health resources and lifestyle behaviors, this study indicate that rural residence is linked to poorer physical activity less access to preventive care higher diabetes complications including kidney problems, vision, wound healing, and dental issues compared with urban setting. Results indicated that socioeconomic status had a significant association

with risk factors, such as family history, smoking, drinking water, and complication, hypertension, and kidney problems, lower socioeconomic conditions with poorer diabetes outcomes corresponds with higher risks and worse outcomes.

CONCLUSION

Findings of this study concluded that Sociodemographic characteristics, life style behaviors and environmental factors such as age, education, income, residence and diet practices, significantly affect lifestyle behaviors, and the progress of complications among patients with Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus. Poor glycemic control unhealthy lifestyle were common among patients especially among rural, low education and income participants. Improving public awareness, strengthening health education, promoting healthy lifestyle behaviors, and improving access to healthcare services especially for rural and low-income populations are essential steps to reduce the burden of diabetes complications and improve the quality of life of diabetic patients.

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